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TAILORED POLYMER NETWORKS BY SEQUENTIAL THIOL-ENE PHOTOPOLYMERIZATION

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#ICCM22

Structural control of PEG-co-TEG network

Same stoichiometry, different structure...

- Random copolymer network ($2A_3+B_2+2B_2'$)

- Alternating copolymer network ($A_2BA_2+2B_2'$)

... and different properties

DMTA

Alternating PEG-co-TEG polymer networks:

- prevent PEGDA homopolymerization
- crosslink density is lower because of this, which reduces T_g
- thiol conversion is higher, which suppresses odour and tackiness